
**ADOPTION AND USAGE OF TECHNOLOGY-DRIVEN BANKING SERVICES IN
COMMERCIAL BANKS: A STUDY IN VIRUDHUNAGAR DISTRICT**

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INTRODUCTION

After demonetization, the tradition of digital banking has gained more weightage and the Indian banks are very busy in delivering e-banking and internet banking services even to customers of rural and remote India. Hence in this transformation stage from conventional banking to contemporary banking, there is a strong need to understand the level of satisfaction of bank customers about technological up gradations in banks. Their demographic profile variables including age, sex, education and monthly income may influence the levels of satisfaction towards modern banking services. The researcher has taken efforts to present the attitude of customers towards e-banking services in Virudhunagar district.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

“High Tech E- banking” facilities to the customers to access their accounting transactions very easily and within short span of time. They concluded that what the corporate customers expect from their bankers are reliability, assurance, empathy, responsiveness and pro-activity as they are the back bone of any relationship(Mahalakshmi,V., and Kanchana, P.Na., 2015). Today is re-defined and re-engineered with the use of Information Technology and it is sure that the future of banking will offer more sophisticated services to the customers with the continuous product and process innovations.(Satinder Singh, and Ajaydeep Singh Brar.,2016).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the present study is outlined below

- To analyse the level of the adoption towards tech-based banking services.

HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis is a tentative proposition formulated for empirical testing. The study is explorative in nature. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher has framed the following hypotheses:

- H₀1: There is no significant difference among types of tech-based banking services preferred by the respondents

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- H₀₂: There is no significant difference among the respondents regarding period of using tech-based banking services.

METHODOLOGY

The survey has been undertaken to analyze the customer satisfaction towards tech-based services. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Commercial banks can be classified into public, private sector banks and foreign banks. There are one hundred and thirty-four public sector banks, seventy-one private sector banks and there are no foreign banks in Virudhunagar district and totally two hundred and five bank branches are operating within the limit of Virudhunagar district. Virudhunagar district consist of three revenue divisions namely Aruppukottai, Sivakasi and Sattur. The Virudhunagar district consists of nine taluks namely Aruppukottai, Virudhunagar, Tiruchuli, Kariapatti, Sivakasi, Srivilliputtur, Sattur, Rajapalayam and Vembakottai. On the basis of this sample size calculation, the researcher has taken 100 banks as samples. Then by using proportionate sampling, has selected sixty five public sector banks (134/205*100) and thirty five private sector banks (71/205*100). Totally one hundred banks are selected in the study area. Then, Convenience sampling technique has been adopted for selecting a sample of 500 customers that is 5 customers from each bank branch selected.

The data collected are classified and analyzed keeping in view the objective of the study. For the purpose of analysis, the statistical tools such as Percentage, Two way Analysis of Variance, Weighted Ranking Technique, t-test, One Way ANOVA have been used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

The demographic profile of the respondents was obtained by using seven parameters namely gender, age, marital status, employment wise classification, occupation, monthly income and education qualification. The same is presented in the Table 1

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factor	Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	285	57
	Female	215	43
	Total	500	100.0
Age (in years)	Below 30	243	48.6
	30-40	143	28.6
	40-50	83	16.6
	50 and above	31	6.2

	Total	500	100.0
Marital Status	Married	337	67.4
	Unmarried	163	32.6
	Total	500	100
Employment Wise Classification	Employed	392	78.4
	Unemployed	108	21.6
	Total	500	100.0
Occupation of Employed Respondents	Businessmen	134	34.2
	Private Employee	69	17.6
	Government Employee	126	32.1
	Professionals	47	12.0
	Agriculturist	16	4.1
	Total	392	100.0
Monthly Income (in ₹.)	Less than 5,000	39	9.9
	5,000-10,000	53	13.5
	10,000-15,000	77	19.6
	Above 15,000	223	57.0
	Total	392	100.0
Educational Qualification	Primary Level	17	3.4
	High School	6	1.2
	Higher Secondary	15	3.0
	Under Graduate	165	33.0
	Post Graduate	218	43.6
	Professionals	79	15.8
	Total	500	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 reveals that a majority of 57 per cent of the respondents are male; a majority of 75 per cent of the respondents age group are 30 years below; a majority of 67.4 per cent of the respondents are married; 78.4 per cent of the respondents are employed; 34.2 per cent of the respondents are businessmen; 57 per cent of the respondents fall under the income scale of above ₹15,000; 43.6 per cent of the respondents are post graduates.

II. LEVEL OF ADOPTION OF TECH-BASED BANKING SERVICES**1. Frequency of Using Tech-Based Services**

Today carrying huge money is old fashioned and usage wherever carrying plastic money (cards) is stylish, modern and safe. Now-a-days bank customers prefer to use tech-based banking services rather than going to the bank. The usage of banking services by the customers can be listed under ATM/Debit cards, credit cards, telephone banking, mobile banking, internet banking and ECS/RTGS/NEFT. Table 2

gives cross tabulation of types of tech-based banking services and period of using tech-based banking services.

Table 2
Types of Tech-Based Banking Services and Frequency of Using Tech-Based Banking Services Cross Tabulation

Services/ Years	Not using e-services	Less than 1 year	1 year to 3 years	3 years to 5 years	5 years and above	Total
ATM / Debit cards	0	183 (36.6)	29 (5.8)	95 (19.0)	193 (38.6)	500 (100)
Credit Cards	85 (17.0)	368 (73.6)	11 (2.2)	2 (0.4)	34 (6.8)	500 (100)
Telephone Banking	409 (81.8)	73 (14.6)	16 (3.2)	1 (0.2)	1 (0.2)	500 (100)
Mobile Banking	135 (27)	332 (66.4)	9 (1.8)	21 (4.2)	3 (0.6)	500 (100)
Internet Banking	60 (12.0)	194 (38.8)	209 (41.8)	13 (2.6)	24 (4.8)	500 (100)
ECS/RTGS/NEFT	103 (20.6)	296 (59.2)	72 (14.4)	5 (1.0)	24 (4.8)	500 (100)

Source: Primary data (Figures in parentheses are percentages)

Two way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) has been used to analyse the relationship between types of tech-based banking services preferred by the respondents and period of using tech-based banking services. The null hypotheses framed are as follows:

H₀1: There is no significant difference among types of tech-based banking services preferred by the respondents

H₀2: There is no significant difference among the respondents regarding period of using tech-based banking services.

Table 3
Types of Tech- Based Banking Services and Frequency of Using Tech-Based Banking Services -ANOVA Test Results

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Rows	0	5	0	0	1	2.71089
Columns	214636	4	53659	5.328	0.0044	2.866081
Error	201418	20	10070.9			
Total	416054	29				

Source: Computed data

Regarding the types of tech-based banking services, the calculated value of 'F' is 0 which is not significant as its p value is greater than 0.05 (1>0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, it is

proved that there is no significant difference among types of tech-based banking services preferred by the respondents.

Regarding the period of using tech-based banking services, the calculated value of 'F' is 5.328 which is significant as its p value is less than 0.05 ($0.0044 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it is proved that there is a significant difference among the respondents regarding the period of using tech-based banking services.

2. Factors Influencing to Use Technology Based Banking Services

For successful implementation of e-banking program, it is imperative on the part of bankers to understand why customers prefer an offering and they devise the marketing strategies accordingly. Weighted ranking technique has been used to analyse the factors influencing the customers to use technology based banking services. The results of the weighted ranking technique are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4
Factors Influencing to Use Technology based Banking Services-
Result of Weighted Ranking Technique

Factors	Weighted Mean Score	Ranks
Convenience (Any time banking)	10.03	V
Protection against fraud	8.33	VI
Greater control over finances	6.70	XI
Accessibility	11.95	II
Curiosity	7.21	IX
Paying bill online/ Online Shopping	10.62	III
Real time information	7.26	VIII
User friendliness	12.87	I
Ticket Booking/ Transfer money	6.87	X
Mobility	8.09	VII
Security and privacy through encryption	10.06	IV

Source: Computed data

It is clear from the table 4 that user friendliness got the first rank with mean score of 12.87; accessibility secured second rank with mean score of 11.95 and greater control over finance occupied last rank with the least score of 6.70.

SUGGESTIONS

- Customers should themselves make some efforts to get knowledge and updates about tech based banking services and make them technically competent.
- Different mobile applications for different services would be uncomfortable while using. Therefore, single application for all the services might be designed.

CONCLUSION

Money plays an important role in the day - to - day life. The implementation of tech-based banking service improves customer relation and facilitates the bank to extend the services to the remote areas. Technology deployment should be accompanied by process changes to derive enduring benefits which would enable the banks to manage their banking business in the best possible manner.

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